

THE EUROPEAN UNION EXPERIENCE OF INDUSTRY LOCALIZATION.

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Annotation. Localization of production in industrial enterprises allows to effectively solve problems such as employment in the country, dependence on imports, modernization of industrial enterprises, creation of new industries. It is appropriate to study and use the experiences of the developed European Union countries in the proper organization of the localization process. The article examines the experiences of localization of industrial production in the countries of the European Union and draws the necessary conclusions.

Keywords: industry, localization, industrial production, localization of industrial production.

Localization of production is often carried out by companies seeking to expand the market for their products. As a rule, they take into account the principles of the industrial policy of the country of localization, which allows to rely on state support measures for the national economy or to introduce restrictions and even bans on the import of certain goods.

When it comes to localization, first of all, it is important to study the experience of the developed countries of the world, including the United States of America, the countries of the European Union, China, and the countries of Southeast Asia. Among the main factors of the development of the economy of these countries, it is necessary to list the investment attractiveness of the countries, the strength of the legal framework and, of course, the human capital.

Of course, we can witness that each country has a different approach to the development of its industrial network based on its geographical location, natural resources, population income, and international markets.

In the industry of EU countries, the number of small enterprises is 96% of the total existing enterprises, the number of medium-sized enterprises is 3.1%, and the number of large enterprises is 0.8% [1].

If we analyze by country, the ratio of the number of small industrial enterprises to the total number of enterprises is the lowest in Luxembourg, which is 84.5%.

The ratio of the number of medium-sized industrial enterprises to the total number of industrial enterprises is the lowest in Greece and Slovakia, which is 1.3%. In turn, the ratio of large industrial enterprises to the total industrial enterprises in the country is the lowest in Greece, which is 0.2%.

Large enterprises with the largest index are Luxembourg (3.6%), medium-sized enterprises - Luxembourg (11.9%), small enterprises - Greece (98.4%).

It can be seen that small enterprises form the basis of industrial enterprises in the European Union. It is explained by the fact that it does not require large investment as a well-known advantage of small production.

As of April 1, 2022, the total number of enterprises operating in Uzbekistan is 92,064, which is 17% of the total number of enterprises (542,672). The number of small business entities operating in the industry is 91,969 [2].

According to the results of the analysis, the ratio of small industrial enterprises to total industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan is 99.8%.

If we compare with the countries of the European Union, it shows that the largest figure is 1.4% more than Greece.

From the above, we can conclude that we should pay attention to large enterprises in localization processes. Or they understand that we need to further develop small industrial enterprises and gradually transfer them to a group of medium or large organizations.

In turn, it is natural to ask whether quantity is important or quality.

Industry is the basis of restructuring of agricultural production. By providing it with new equipment, farmers, companies, farms and entities operating in other forms will be economically and culturally raised to a higher level, the important differences between the city and the countryside will be eliminated, and peasant labor will be reduced. helps to turn it into industrial work. Industry is a material source of the country's defense capability, an important factor in maintaining peace in the world, and an important sector that ensures the independence and unity of countries. For example, the role and importance of industry in strengthening the defense capabilities of our country is incomparable. Political, economic and organizational aspirations of all countries, economic cooperation is also reflected in the industrial sector.

Industry is of great importance in the expansion of opportunities to use natural and labor resources, scientific and technical achievements. Industry is characterized by the continuous development of science and technology and the increase in the level of armament with the achievements of production. It makes extensive use of advanced 16 achievements in the field of electrification and electronicization, computerization and chemicalization, production modernization, technical and technological restructuring. He uses them only for peaceful purposes. Industry is the main branch of material production, the foundation of the economy. Only a large-scale mechanized industry capable of restructuring all sectors of the national economy can be the material basis of independence [3].

According to the contribution of real sector enterprises to the GDP, small enterprises make up 16.8%, medium enterprises 18.1%, and large enterprises 65.1% in the whole European Union [4].

The largest indicators in this regard are in small enterprises - Cyprus (45.1%), Italy (33.9%), Iceland (28.3%), in medium enterprises - Estonia - (42.6%), Iceland (35.1%), Norway (29.7%), in large enterprises - Ireland (87.6%), Germany (73.9%), Sweden (74%).

The lowest indicators are in small enterprises - Ireland (5%), Germany (11.4%), Sweden (11.8%), in medium enterprises - Ireland (7.4%), France (12.5%), Sweden (14.2%), in large enterprises - Cyprus (24.2%), Estonia (27.4%), Portugal (36.3%) [5].

In the real sectors of the EU countries, the contribution of large enterprises to the GDP is also large, and we believe that it is appropriate to pay more attention to large enterprises in the investment policy of our country and localization programs.

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